

Determinants of youth unemployment and Vulnerability: A Case of Bukoba Municipality and Muleba District

1. Dr. Domitilla Rwezaula Bashemera

Institute of Rural Development Planning, Dodoma, Tanzania

Contact: domirweza@gmail.com

2. Ms. Grace Benedict

Institute of Rural development Planning, Lake Zone, Mwanza, Tanzania

Contact: grace.benedict@yahoo.com

3. Mr. Sospeter Berling

Institute of Rural Development Planning, Dodoma, Tanzania

Contact: bsospeter@irdp.ac.tz

Abstract

The study was conducted at Bukoba Municipality and Muleba District council, intending to examine the determinants of unemployment and vulnerability. About 1305 households were covered. Primary data were gathered through census by the aid of structured questionnaires. Descriptive statistics and Logistic regression models were deployed for data analysis. The study found that sex and duration for searching employment were statistically significant and had positive influence on youth being unemployed. Sex were 1.1 and duration of searching for employment 6 months to one year was 4.1 and more than 2 years was 6.5 times more likely to influence youth unemployment respectively. Regarding to vulnerability, unemployment was highly statistically significant ($p < 0.001$) in influencing youth inability to access health services, pursue further education and lack of participation in leadership and giving out their opinions. Unemployed youth were more than 13 times and 16 times their employed counterparts to suffer vulnerability in lack access to health services and further education respectively. The study recommends that development actors should develop gender and age specific youth employment strategies. Female should be targeted for better quality education to enable them qualify for employment. The study recommends that the government should strengthen the informal sector and encourage them to create more employment opportunities. Also the youth should be encouraged to be employed in the informal sector which does not require experience which majority of youth.

Key Words: Youth, Unemployment Vulnerability

1.0 Introduction

Unemployed refers to person aged (15 – 64) who during the reference period were currently available for work, actively seeking for work, but were without work (URT, 2017). Globally there has been an increasing trend of youth unemployment. According to the ILO's Global Employment Trends for Youth, 2011 Update (www.ilo.org), the global youth unemployment rate rose from 11.8 to 12.7 percent between 2008 and 2009. In the ten years from 1998 and 2008, youth unemployment increased by a total of 0.2 percent or about 100,000 persons per year; but from 2008 to 2009 it increased by 5.3% or 4.5 million persons in a single year. By the end of 2010, an estimated 75.8 million young people were unemployed (UN, "World Youth Report," 2012). Despite unemployment being a global concern, the situation has continued to be worse in least developed countries. Tanzania is an example of the least developed country that has failed to utilize the active labour force population. For example the estimates of unemployed persons for year 2011 were 2,368,672 persons which is equivalent to 10.7% of the labour force population (NBS, 2011). Guloba, 2015 highlighted gender and urban-rural differences in youth unemployment whereby, 13.4 percent of youth aged 15-34 years was not employed. The unemployment rate among youth stood at 14.3 percent of female and 12.3 percent of male. Urban areas were hardest hit with unemployment rate, reaching 22.3 percent against 7.1 percent in rural areas.

The causes of unemployment among youths are that most youth have no skills for employment. The skills requirement in the labour market is not compatible with the skills supply; as a result, the global labour market competitiveness and the increased use of advanced technology and ICT replace labour and require labour with specialized skills (Guardian 2014). The growing aspirations to acquire degrees or equivalent qualifications has led many institutions responsible for technical/tertiary education to be converted into higher learning institutions with far reaching implications on the balance of ratios between engineers, technicians and artisans (URT, 2016). There is population growth leading to increase of youth entrance into labour force. For example, it is estimated that over 800,000 young men and women enter the labour market every year (Kikwete, 2015). This has made unemployment rate to be 2,291,785 (10.3 percent) (NBS, 2014). Unemployment underscores the importance of creating a conducive environment for business to flourish so that more jobs are created. Minja (2015) recommended to the decision-makers at all levels to mobilize the key actors in their respective regions to ensure youth employment is taken seriously into their different agendas. Also making the goal of decent and productive employment for youth a national

priority; promote access to employment opportunities and resources by the vulnerable and marginalized population youth, and people with disability (*youth employment decade, 2014*)

About 5% of the council's budget every year is allocated for youth development to enable them to engage in business and enterprises. The government enacted the Business Activity Registration Act of 2005 of which the Business Registration Licensing Agency (BRELA) was established to register business; government also established the National Youth Development Policy which addresses the adverse impacts of social-economic problems, such as unemployment and poverty (URT, 2007). Despite such efforts, the youths still fear to enter into business; those in business are operating on informal basis, as these youth are not informed on the diversity of information related on employment and business undertakings.

2.0 Unemployment and vulnerability

ILO and EU (2012) assert that the unemployed comprise all persons of working age who were without work during the reference period, available for work, but not in paid employment or self-employment currently; this implies that they were available for paid employment or self-employment during the reference period and seeking work in a specified recent period to seek paid employment or self-employment, and they did not get one. The National Employment Policy (URT, 2008), defined Unemployment as a situation of total lack of work of an individual. It can be viewed as an enforced idleness of potential wage earners or self employed persons that are able and willing to work, but cannot find work (URT, 2014).

Baah-oateng (2013) found unemployment to be a bigger labour market challenge for men than women from 1960, until 2000 when the reverse occurred. Moreover, Kingdom and Knight (2004) observed an increase in the probability of an urban dweller becoming unemployed by 8.6 percentage in South Africa. In Tanzania, like in other countries of the world, youth unemployment is affecting the age cohort of the population which is most economically active and economic productive and reproductive. For example, Baah-oateng (2013), found that youth lack of job search experience and labour market information to facilitate their job acquisition. Even in times of economic upturn, lack of work experience combined with lack of social capital puts the youth at the disadvantage for new job opportunities. The Government set ambitious targets to reduce youth unemployment rates from 10% to 5% by 2015 (URT, 2008). In the Tanzania Integrated Labour Force Survey (ILFS) of 2006, active labour force (15–64 years) was estimated at 18.8

million people, whereby 9.7 million were females and 9.0 million were males. The survey also revealed that 11.7% of the total labour force in the country, about 2.2 million were unemployed, out of whom 53% were youths (URT, 2007). This has resulted in the cumulative detrimental effects as youth live without hope.

For example, due to economic hardship, they live in squatter settlements characterized by overcrowding, poor sanitation, increased crime rates, and inadequate social services (Liviga and Mekacha, 1998). Many of them are highly engaged in unproductive activities, like playing pool and drinking during working hours. Young girls are vulnerable to sexual exploitation and violence, contracting HIV and AIDS, sexually transmitted infections, and unwanted pregnancies (RDT, 2011). Moreover, Paul and Moser (2009) cited by Moller (2011) reported that, Unemployment also has negative influence to the health of other family members, and family support has been found to mediate the negative effects of unemployment.

Vulnerability is defined as the probability of suffering a decline in wellbeing. Thus a person, household or community is vulnerable to the degree that they are likely to be poorer tomorrow than today (URT, 2004). Philip & Rayhan (2004), cited in UNDP, (2004) defined vulnerability as "a human condition or process resulting from physical, social, economic and environmental factors, which determine the likelihood and scale of impact from the impact of a given hazard". Social vulnerability refers to the inability of people, organizations, and societies to withstand adverse impacts from multiple stressors to which they are exposed. These impacts are due in part to characteristics inherent in social interactions, institutions, and systems of cultural values (URT, 2004). ILO (2010) argued that workers in vulnerable employment as the sum of own-account workers and contributing family workers. They are less likely to have formal work arrangements, and are therefore more likely to lack decent working conditions, adequate social security and voice through effective representation by trade unions and similar organizations. Vulnerable employment is often characterized by inadequate earnings, low productivity and difficult conditions of work that undermine workers' fundamental rights. Lerisse, et al. (2003) argue poverty is a description of how things are now, while vulnerability is how things might be in future with respect to individual's position on the poverty line what determine vulnerability to poverty.

A high level of un-employment and underemployment is one of the critical socio-economic problems facing Ethiopia. While the labour force grows, with an increasing proportion of youth, employment growth is inadequate to absorb labour market entrants. As a result, youth are especially affected by unemployment. Moreover, young people are more likely to be employed in

jobs of low quality, underemployed, working long hours for low wages, engaged in dangerous work or receive only short term and/or informal employment arrangements (Denu et al, 2005).

Vulnerability describe on how things might be in future with respect to individual's position on the poverty line. It is possible to determine the movement from vulnerability to poverty. When the individual suffers a decline in her well being, the level of his or her resources or assets available to that individual suffer too. It is the individual's access to assets that determines his or her capacity to respond (Lerisse, et al., 2003). Vulnerability is, therefore, an important aspect of poverty reduction policy and implementation, as it engages the analysis of poverty more dynamically by extending policy concerns to impoverishing forces as illustrated in the in Figure 1.

At point (a) a non-poor individual or a household far away from the poverty line experiences a situation whose impact is too strong to cope with and that brings the household to point aa, which is very close to the poverty line. The household has suffered a decline in well-being, but has not crossed the poverty line yet. At point (b) an individual who was non-poor, but very close to the poverty line, suffered from a situation whose impact was strong and that s/he could not cope and has been forced to cross the poverty line into situation bb.

Figure 1. Vulnerability Processes

Source: Lerisse, et al. (2003)

He or she has become impoverished as his or her income or expenditure is below the poverty line. S/he is now poor as his/her income or expenditure is below the poverty line. At point (c) an individual was already poor but

because of a certain situation's/he becomes poorer and thus crosses the extreme poverty line into situation cc. S/he is poorer than before. In the three scenarios described above, the risk of being impoverished becomes real. But the individual in scenario one was able to cope with the impoverishing factors to the extent that he or she did not cross the poverty line. Those in scenario b and c could not cope with the situations, and thus became poorer. This implies that youth when are young are well of as they usually get supports from their parents, the more they grow up the more they need employment to be independent. Since employment is difficult to obtain they move towards the poor situation. However, Namibia Statistics Agent (2015) addressed vulnerable employment as referred to is measured as the sum of own account workers and those contributing as family workers as a proportion of total employment. In 2012, 68,386 youth were in vulnerable employment. In 2013 this figure more than dropped slightly to reach 63,485. Most of the vulnerable workers are female (42.8% in 2012 and 47.2% in 2013). The majority of the vulnerable employed youth in 2013 was in the rural areas (66.5% in 2012 and 65.7% in 2013).

ILO (2010) urged that in developed economies with strong social protection measures, workers who lose their jobs can move into unemployment, generally resulting in an overall decline in total employment. In many developing economies, on the other hand, workers who lose their jobs do not have access to social protection schemes. Rather than becoming unemployed, these workers often take up various forms of employment, working on their own accounts, or contributing to family businesses. This, in turn, results in an increase in the number of workers in vulnerable employment. Measures have been done to address youth unemployment, such as establishing a fully-fledged Department of Youth to deal with youth issues including unemployment; putting in place a National Development Policy (URT, 2007), a policy addressing creation of human resource development opportunities for the acquisition of demand driven skills and competencies for wage and self-employment. Another initiative towards youth employment is the National Employment Policy of 2008 aiming at enhancing the promotion of youth employment (URT, 2008). There has also been the establishment of Youth Revolving Fund in Local Government Authorities to support youth income generating activities in organized economic production brigades and small entrepreneurs. Local government authorities contribute 5% of their budget to this fund. Moreover, Vocation Education and Training programs have been developed since 1995. Despite the efforts done to address youth employment, more persons were unemployed in 2000/1 than in 1990/1. For example, Trading Economics (2007) reported that Youth Unemployment Rate in Tanzania decreased to

13.70 percent in 2014 from 14.90 percent in 2006. Youth Unemployment Rate in Tanzania averaged 14.30 percent from 2006 until 2014, reaching an all time high of 14.90 percent in 2006 and a record low of 13.70 percent in 2014.

Youth labour market in Tanzania is influenced by the growth performance of the economy. At the time when the economy is growing slowly, there is inability of the economy to create sufficient employment opportunities, youths and adults are likely to suffer the problem of unemployment. Among youths, however, the problem of unemployment is more severe due to their rapid rate of increase into the labour market and the increasing magnitude of the new entrants. In Tanzania for example estimated 7000 unemployed youths join the reserve of unemployed labour force annually. The causes of youth unemployment are diverse, apart from economic growth performance, youth tend to suffer from problems, including lack of relevant education and skills, lack adequate training. Lack of experience, lack of information about employment opportunities, and their employability (Mjema, 1997); there is also an aspect of cultural factors where female youths are not preferred in some jobs due to belief that their role is confined to household duties which often are unpaid or underpaid.

As the formal employment sector tends to remain narrow, the unemployed youths opts to join the informal sector to sustain their livelihood. However, the effectiveness of the informal sector in Tanzania to absorb unemployed youths has faced a number of constraints, among which lack of practical business skills, lack of capital to start business, lack of experience and the unfriendly business environment, where youth fail to engage in self employment and income generating activities (Bagachwa,1991; Luvanga, 1994; Mjema, 1997).

The problem of unemployment affect greatly the youths in various ways, some falling into extreme poverty others suffering different forms of social and economic deprivations. Inability of youth to engage in meaningful employment has lead to lack of access to health services, leadership and managerial skills as well as increase in poverty vulnerability (Young leaders' think tank for policy alternatives, 2014). Various studies have linked youth unemployment with vulnerability including inability to access quality health services, further education, education for children and lack of community participation. For example, according to Mohamed (2014), unemployed youth have limited access to education, social services, health care and undignified living conditions. Young communist league of South Africa, 2016 found that the health status of youth is related to the level of education and whether or not one is employed. It was argued that, a high percentage of

those with higher education and those who are employed reported that they enjoy a high percentage of good health unlike those who were unemployed.

Watts (2010), writing for the OECD, recognized the importance of relevant labour market information. This implies that youth have right information on the labour market. To address this problem, Syrett (2008) recommended establishing a strong evidence base and local intelligence which enables an understanding of the workings of the local labour market, the barriers faced by different groups, and the differing aspirations and motivations of those not economically active, before establishing a plan of what needs to be done locally with the role of different agencies in achieving this.

3.0 The issue and methodology

This study seeks to understand the phenomenon of youth unemployment and its implications to youth vulnerability. The study focuses on youth who are productive and reproductive members of the society. Specifically the study intended to determine the causes of youth unemployment in Muleba and Bukoba Districts and investigate the link between youth employment and vulnerability. This study was conducted in Bukoba Municipality and Muleba District. The 2002 National Population and Housing Census (NBS, 2004) indicated that Bukoba Municipality is dominated by business operations which account for 39% of the total labour force. On the other hand, the census showed that in Muleba District, employment in business operations account for 6% of the total labour force, office work, agriculture, fishing, elementary occupations and plant operations. According to Bukoba and Muleba District Council profiles, the estimated number of entrepreneurial activities is 2,231 and 2,328 respectively. The main cash crops include coffee, sugarcane, and tea while the main food crops include bananas, beans, cassava, sorghum and maize. The youths are involved in a range of businesses including banana, fruits and vegetable selling, motorcycle business, running small shops and kiosks. Those in urban wards are dealing with mobile phones money transfer activities and stationery sales.

Primary data were gathered through a census using a structured set of questionnaires that were used to collect data from the selected study villages and mitaa. This study, in particular, used a community-based monitoring system (CBMS), which entails the participation of people in the community to collect data, process and use data. The system provided information on the socio-economic welfare conditions of all members of the community. All households in the selected Mitaa and villages were involved in the interview, a total of 5190 household members from 1305 households were covered.

The study covered 1,953 youth aged (15 – 35 Years) as shown in the diagram below.

Figure 1: Youth sampling in Muleba and Bukoba Municipality

Source: CBMS Census in Bukoba Municipality and Muleba District Council, Tanzania, 2016

Three project team members and two District statistics Officers supervised the data collection exercise. Eight enumerators were selected and trained to administer the questionnaire by using the CBMS Accelerated Poverty Profiling. Information on variables stipulated in the questionnaire was collected from the heads of households and the selected youths to respond on youth related questions. Additional information was collected from key informants. Interviews and focus group discussion were deployed. Secondary data were sought from the National Integrated Labour force survey, National integrated Business survey, and the Tanzania Human Development Report of 2014.

Data were collected using tablets, validated and sent to the CBMS Portal. Data were transformed to excel, corrected and imported into Stata and SPSS version 20 to make a dataset ready to be used for analysis. Tables were used for data presentation. In order to reach logistic regression, cross tabulation was performed; the variables which were significant were considered for further analysis by using logistic regression model.

The study identified the determinants of youth unemployment in the study sites, investigated the link between youth employment and vulnerability. Logistic regression models were deployed to assess the factors influencing youth unemployment in general and youth employment in the informal sector. In order to use logistic regression, there was definition of dependent variables and independent variables.

The study involved nine independent variables (X) and two dependent variables (Y). Each dependent variable was regressed against 9 independent variables (X). The response was recorded into a binary (0, 1) scale. For example, if a factor has influenced unemployment, then $y= 1$, otherwise $y=0$, where, factor 1, 2, 3....9.

The logistic regression model for unemployment factors is defined by

$$\text{Logit}(Y) = \ln\left(\frac{p}{1-p}\right) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \dots + \beta_n X_n + \varepsilon$$

Where as:

$$Y = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if unemployed} \\ 0 & \text{if employed} \end{cases} \quad \text{and} \quad Y = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if vulnerable} \\ 0 & \text{if not vulnerable} \end{cases}$$

P is the probability of the factor to influence and $\beta_i, i=0, 1, \dots, 9$ are the respective parameters to be estimated

Whereas:

β_0 =Constant term; X = Independent variables (Unemployment factors); β_n = Logistic coefficients for the independent variables and ε = Error term

Independent variables (Determinants of Youth unemployment)

β_0 = Constant; X_1 = Sex; X_2 = Duration for searching employment; X_3 = Marital status; X_4 = Location; X_5 = Ward; X_6 = Age; X_7 = Entrepreneurial skills; X_8 = Mobile phone; X_9 = Work experiences; and ε = Error n

Logistic regression models were employed to assess the link between youth unemployment and vulnerability.

4.0 Results and Discussion

The descriptive analysis shows that a total of 5190 population were involved in the census. Youth were about 1,953(37.63 percent) of whom about 1542(29.71 percent) and about 909(17.51 percent) were male from Bukoba Municipality and Muleba district council respectively. Moreover, youth male were 587(30.06 percent) from Bukoba and 286(14.64 percent) from Muleba district. With regards to sex about 1,669 (32.16 percent) and 1,070(20.62 percent) were female in Bukoba municipality and Muleba district council. Also about 732(37.48 percent) and 348(17.82 percent) were youth in both districts. Labour force in the study area was accounting at 2,886 people of

which 1,936 (67.08 percent) were youth. 583(30.06 percent) and 282(14.57 percent) were male youth from Bukoba Municipality and Muleba district council. About 849 people were employed from whom about 483(56.89 percent) were youth of which 290(34.16 percent) of were males and 193(22.73 percent) and 193(22.72 percent) were female. These result implies that few female are employed compared to their male counterparts. About 2,037 populations were found to be unemployed. About 1,453(71.33 percent) were youth from whom 574(28.18 percent) were male and 193(22.73 percent) were female. This result implies that there is high rate unemployment among youth in the study area.

Logistic regression was used to get information on the determinants of youth unemployment and vulnerability. Determinants of youth unemployment included sex, duration searching employment, marital status, location, Ward, age, entrepreneurial skills, ownership of mobile phones and work experience. Table 1 shows the level of significant in which each variable influence youth unemployment

The CBMS findings in Table 1 show the result of the first model. Each determinant variable is associated with either increased or decreased odd of influencing youth unemployment. The results in the model show that being a female and the duration of searching for employment had high and positive influence on a youth being unemployed. Female were 1.1 times more likely to be unemployed compared to their male counterparts. Duration of searching for employment 6 months to one year was 4.1 and more than 2 years was 6.5 times more likely to influence youth unemployment respectively.

Table 1: Determinants of Youth Unemployment

Determinants	Model 1: Determinant of unemployment	
	Coef.	95% Conf. Interval
Sex		
Male (RC)	1.0	
Female	1.1***	0.7 - 1.5
Duration searching employment		
Less than 6 Months (RC)	1.0	
6 months to 1 year	4.1***	2.1 - 6.1
More than 2 years	6.5***	4.4 - 8.5
Marital Status		
Never Married (RC)	1.0	
Married	-0.3	-0.9 - 0.3
Divorced	0.6	-1.1 - 2.3
Separated	-1.5*	-3.0 - -0.0

Widowed	0.1	-2.5 - 2.8
Living together	-1.2*	-2.2 - -0.2
Location		
Rural (RC)	1.0	
Urban	-0.2	-1.6 - 1.2
Ward		
Nshambya (RC)	1.0	
Kahororo	-0.0	-0.7 - 0.7
Nshamba	-0.4	-1.8 - 1.1
Kamachumu	0.0	-1.4 - 1.4
Age		
15-19 (RC)	1.0	
20-24 years	-1.6***	-2.3 - -0.9
25-29 years	-2.2***	-3.0 - -1.4
30-35 years	-2.3***	-3.1 - -1.4
Entrepreneurial skills		
Masonry	0.7	-0.5 - 2.0
Welding	-0.1	-1.9 - 1.7
Bricks making	1.8*	0.2 - 3.3
Tailoring	-0.3	-1.3 - 0.6
Gardening	-1.0	-2.9 - 0.9
Mobile Phone ownership		
Not owning mobile phone (RC)	1.0	
Own mobile phone	0.4	-0.2 - 1.0
Work experience		
Not having Experience (RC)	1.0	
Have work experience	0.5*	0.0 - 1.0
_cons	1.3	-0.4 - 3.0

Key: *=0.05, **<0.01 and ***<0.001

Source: CBMS Census in Bukoba and Muleba District Tanzania, 2016

While sex and duration for search of employment had positive association, age shows a negative association. The probability of a youth being unemployed has decreased by age. For example, youth aged 20-24 years the probability of being unemployed decreased by 0.6 percent, youth aged 25-29 decreased by 120 percent and youth aged 30 to 35 years decreased by 130 percent. Results on gender disparities in youth unemployment concur with the findings of the study by Denu et al, (2005) in Ethiopia which found more (3.9%) of female youth aged 20-24 were not employed compared to (23.2%) of male youth in the same age category. When comparing unemployment among youth by their age groups, those aged 15-19 years seem to be at higher risk of not being employed. However, the highest educational attainment of majority youth in the study area was primary

education. Therefore, lack of ability to proceed with further education at age of 15-19 youth in the study area feel as they are ready and available for work but they don't have employment opportunities.

These results can be cemented by the findings of UNDP in Kenya, which suggested that low participation of youth aged 15 – 24 years is articulated by the transition period of schooling and from school to home where they have not yet entered in employment although they might be ready and available for work. However, the results from Logistic regression show that work experience is less than likely to influence unemployment, but is significant ($p=0.05$). Other challenges are that youth lack required technical academic qualification. The option of informal sector experience as an obstacle is not visible here the problem is capital. Youths are lacking capital to engage into entrepreneurship.

Youth unemployment and vulnerability considered the inability to access health services, further education, support children's education and community participation. The result in Table 2 indicates that all variables were not significant in influencing inability to access health services, except two variables (employment status and income levels). Unemployment was highly statistically significant ($p<0.001$) in influencing inability to access health services and it was more than 13 times compared to those who reported to be employed. These results are supported by the study of young leaders' think tank for policy alternatives (2014). It found that inability of youth to engage in meaningful employment has lead to lack of access to health services, leadership and managerial skills as well as increase in poverty vulnerability. This implies that unemployed youth are not able to generate income which can be used to access quality health services. On the other side, the type of employment was not statistically significant. Whereby, income levels and ward were less significant in influencing youth inability to access health services.

When employment and location were considered on the inability to pursue further education, the result show that not being employed is highly statistically significant ($p<0.001$) and was more than 16 times the employed youth. Regarding to location, there was a negative relationship between rural wards and inability to pursue further education. Youth in rural wards were less than 14 times likely to be unable to pursue further education than youth in the urban wards. This implies that, majority of rural youth do not consider further education important due to their dependence on agriculture which for them does not require higher levels of formal education. When ward was considered, the result show that, Nshamba and Kamachumu wards were highly statistically significant but were less than 13 times likely to influence

the inability to pursue further education. This implies that there is no association between ward and inability to pursue further education

Table 2: Youth Unemployment and Unable health services and unable to pursue further education

	Model 2: Unable health services		Model 3: Unable further education	
	OR Sig	CI 95%	OR Sig.	CI 95%
Employment Status				
Employed (RC)	1.0		1.0	
Not employed	13.2***	11.1 – 15.3	16.6***	14.2 – 18.9
Type of employment				
Formal (RC)	1.0		1.0	
Informal	0.2	-0.3 – 0.8	-0.2	-0.9 – 0.4
Income Level				
Less than 1 USD (RC)	1.0		1.0	
More than 1 USD	-0.7*	-1.3 – 0.0	-0.5	-1.3 – 0.3
Location				
Rural (RC)	1.0		1.0	
Urban	-1.2	-3.4 – 1.0	-13.7	-15.4 - -12.1
Ward				
Nshambya (RC)	1.0		1.0	
Kahororo	0.8	-0.4 – 2.0	0.7	-0.9 – 2.2
Nshamba	-1.1	-3.3 – 1.2	-13.8***	-15.6 - -12.0
Kamachumu	-2.2*	-4.2 - -0.2	-14.3***	-15.5 - -12.8
Cons	1.1	-1.1 – 3.4	13.4***	11.7 – 15.2

Key: * = p<0.05, ** = p<=0.01, and *** = P<0.001

Source: CBMS Census in Bukoba and Muleba District Tanzania, 2016

Results in Table 3, show that employment status, type of employment, income level and location were not statistically significant in influencing access to children education. Only wards were statistically significant, although there were no much difference among rural and urban wards. Also results in the same table indicate that, employment status was highly significant in influencing youth vulnerability in lack of community participation. The unemployed youth were 18 times more likely not participate in leadership and giving out their opinions compared to their employed counterparts. Therefore, an unemployed youth is at risk of being excluded in various development issues which worsen their vulnerability conditions. This result differ with the Australian Research Alliance for

Children and Youth, (2008) who found that the involvement of young people in decision making improves policy and services for youth.

Table 3: Youth Unemployment and unable to meet children education and Lack of community participation

	Model 4: Unable children education		Model 5: Lack of community participation	
	OR Sig.	CI 95%	OR Sig	CI 95%
Employment Status				
Employed (RC)	1.0		1.0	
Not employed	0.5	-0.5 – 1.4	18.0***	-0.5 – 1.4
Type of employment				
Formal employment (RC)	1.0		1.0	
Informal employment	-0.8	-1.8 – 0.1	-0.8	-1.8 – 0.1
Income Level				
Less than 1 USD (RC)	1.0		1.0	
More than 1 USD	-0.3	-1.2 – 0.5	-0.3	-1.2 – 0.5
Location				
Rural (RC)	1.0		1.0	
Urban	-14.6	-16.7 – 12.6	-14.6***	-16.7 – 12.2
Ward				
Nshambya (RC)	1.0		1.0	
Kahororo	-0.5	-2.0 – 1.1	-0.5	-2.0 – 1.1
Nshamba	-14.5***	-16.7 – 12.2	-14.4***	-16.7 – 12.2
Kamachumu	-14.3***	-16.2 – 12.4	-14.3***	-16.2 – 12.4
Cons	13.6***	11.5 – 15.8	11.6***	9.5 – 13.7

Key: * = p<0.05, ** = p<=0.01, and *** = P<0.001

Source: CBMS Census in Bukoba and Muleba District Tanzania, 2016

5.0 Conclusion and recommendations

The survey results have indicated that gender, duration of searching for employment and age are strong determinants of youth unemployment. Female youth are highly affected by unemployment as compared to their male counterparts. Also unemployment problem is big for youths at young age, the situation which necessitates gender and age specific youth employment strategies. Work experience was less significant in influencing youth unemployment since informal employment does not depend much on experience, rather it depends on capital. Unemployment has a strong influence on youth vulnerability. Unemployed youth were more likely to be unable to access health services, unable to pursue further education and lack of participation in leadership and giving out opinions than employed youth. This indicates that if measures are not taken to ensure youth employment, they will continue to be in danger of social exclusion. However they should the target and means to development. The study recommends that the government should strengthen the informal sector and encourage them to creation of more employment opportunities. Also the youth should be encouraged to be employed in the informal sector which does not require experience so that they can use the income earned from employment to access basic needs for themselves and their families.

References

- Australian Research Alliance for Children and Youth (2008) Preventing Youth Disengagement and Promoting Engagement.
- Baah-oateng (2013) Determinant of Unemployment in Ghana. *African Development Review*. Vol.25, No 4, 2013, 385-399
- Bagachwa, M.S.D (1991). Choice of Technology in Industry: The Economics of Grains Milling in Tanzania: International Development Research Centre (IDRC), Ottawa
- Bureau of Labor Statistics, U.S. Department of Labor, *The Economics Daily*, Youth employment and unemployment, July 2014 on the Internet at https://www.bls.gov/opub/ted/2014/ted_20140819.htm (visited April 26, 2017
- Denu, B., Tekeste, A. and Deijl, H. (2005) Characteristics and determinants of youth unemployment, underemployment in Ethiopia. Employment Policies Unit.
- Guardian (2014) Youth unemployment, national priority in Tanzania
- Guloba, M., Mushumba, D., Rajaa Mohamed, Kabanza, K. and Gachugu, E. (2015) Promoting youth employment through entrepreneurship trainings, mentorship and start up capital
- International Labour Organization (2010) Global Employment Trend. International Labour Office. Geneva, 2010.
- International Labour Organization (2011) Labour force framework: Concepts, Definitions, Issues and Classifications. Geneva.
- Kingdom, G. G. and J. Knight (2004), 'Race and the Incidence of Unemployment in South Africa' , *Review of Development Economics*, Vol. 8, No. 2, pp. 198–222.
- Lerisse, F., Mmari, D. and Buruani, M (2003) Vulnerability and Social Protection program in Tanzania,
- Liviga, J. & Mekacha D., K. (1998). Youth migration and poverty alleviation : a case study of petty traders (Wamachinga) in Dar es Salaam [Dar es Salaam] : Research Programme on Poverty Alleviation, c1998.

Research report, 0856-41821 ; no. 98.5

Luvanga, N.E (1994). An overview of Informal Sector in Tanzania. Paper Presented at a Workshop on Users'Needs of Informal Sector Data at Bahari Beach Hotel, Dar es Salaam

Mjema, G.D (1997). Youth Unemployment in Tanzania: New Strategies for Combating an Old Problem. *Journal of Population Studies and Development*, Vol.4, No.1, 1-997

Mohamed, A (2014) Youth Unemployment: A Global Security Challenge/Havard International Review

Moller , H. (2011) Health effects of unemployment Wirral Performance & Public Health Intelligence Team

Mwanjali , S., Teye, A., & Shelukindo, R. (2005) Youth Unemployment in Tanzania. WBI Labor Market Core Course

National Bureau of Statistics (2011). Tanzania in figures 2010. Dar es Salaam: National Bureau of Statistics.

National Bureau of Statistics (2014).The Regional and District Data in Brief, 2012 Population and Housing Census, National Bureau of Statistics, Dar es Salaam.

Paul and Moser (2009) Paul KI, Moser K (2009): Unemployment impairs mental health: Meta-analyses. *Journal of vocational behaviour*; 74: 264-282.

Philip, D. & Rayhan,. I. (2004) Vulnerability and Poverty: What are the causes and how are they related. ZEF Bonn. Center for Development Research.

Syrett, S. (2008), "Worklessness: The Role of Local Action and Local Economic Development", paper produced for the NCRA Panel, Centre for Enterprise and Economic Development Research, Middlesex University.

United Republic of Tanzania (1997) National Youth Development Policy. Dar es Salaam

United Republic of Tanzania (2004) Vulnerability and Resilience to Poverty in Tanzania: Causes, Consequences and Policy Implications, Mkuki na

Nyota. Dar es Salaam, Tanzania.

United Republic of Tanzania (2007). Integrated Labour Force Survey of 2006,

United Republic of Tanzania (2014) Providing Africa's Youth with skills and Training for Jobs. Tanzania Country Reports on Policies and mechanisms for Integration into workforce and Job Creation.

United Republic of Tanzania (2017) Draft National Employment Prime Minister's Office Youth, Employment and Person's with Disabilities

Watts, A. G. (2010), "Career Guidance and Post-Secondary Vocational Education and Training", paper prepared for the OECD Review of Post-Secondary Vocational Education and Training, Skills beyond School, OECD, Paris.

Young Communist League of South Africa, (2016), The Development and Underdevelopment of Youth in South Africa: Discussion Document 2016.

Young leaders' think tank for policy alternatives (2014), A Paper on the Challenges of Youth (UN) Employment in Uganda.